

Indian Sign Language Recognition Using OpenCV and Machine Learning

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Abstract— Deaf and hearing-impaired people utilize sign languages for communication. For effective communication, sign language employs various hand movements. Ordinary people may find it difficult to grasp. To decode the sign languages, a skilled interpreter is required, however this is not always achievable due to a lack of trained professionals. To tackle this, we can utilize a sign language recognition system written in Python based on OpenCV and machine learning. The device can translate sign language into text.

Keywords— *OpenCV, Mediapipe, TensorFlow, Machine learning, Deep learning, Neural networks.*

I. INTRODUCTION

Inability to speak and hear is a true disability, it is a barrier for effective communication. Sign language is a nonverbal form of communication used by the speech and hearing impaired people to communicate with others. Sign languages are referred as the most well-structured and organized means of communication. It differs according to countries and areas. There are various kinds of sign languages such as American Sign Language, Indian Sign Language, Italian Sign Language etc. Due to the diverse nature, it is difficult for the common people to understand. For the speech and hearing-impaired people there is no other way for communication. This will generate a communication gap between common people and speech impaired people. To avoid this, we can use a sign language recognition system using OpenCV, Machine learning, TensorFlow and Mediapipe packages in python. Here we used computer vision-based gesture recognition where camera is used for recognizing these gestures. The feature extracted dataset is used to train the model.

Sign language recognition is an important research area since there are lot of challenges in developing an automatic recognition system. Most of the research are concentrating on American Sign Languages which is easier to recognize as compared to Indian Sign Languages. So, it is important to develop accurate system for recognizing Indian Sign Languages.

II. BASIC TERMINOLOGIES USED

A. *OpenCV*

OpenCV is an opensource library used for computer vision and image processing. It can process images and videos to recognize objects and human faces and gestures. OpenCV in python make use of NumPy, a package highly optimised for solving numerical operations. The OpenCV structures are converted to and from NumPy arrays. The purpose of computer vision is to understand the content of images and video snippets. It extracts necessary details and description from images. It does two functionalities object classification and object identification.

OpenCV is used for computer vision because of it is available free of cost. It requires less RAM. It can be easily integrated with other programming languages.

B. *MediaPipe*

MediaPipe is Googles open-source framework which is used for media processing. It is a framework that is used for Computer Vision and Deep Learning. It helps in building perception pipelines. Perception pipelines can be referred as some sort of audio and video. MediaPipe can be used for posing estimation and real-time hand tracking. Here MediaPipe is used for palm detection and for creating hand landmarks. The perception pipelines are often called Graphs.

C. *Tensorflow*

TensorFlow is an open-source platform used for machine learning. It is designed to make neural networks used for machine learning. It provides collection of workflows for train and test the machine learning models. TensorFlow was developed by google brain team.

III. LITERATURE REVIEW

[1]. Dr. Sabeenian R.S in his research paper recommend a sign language recognition system based on Computer Vision and Deep Learning. He used Modified National Institute of Standards and Technology Dataset for train the model. But the model can recognise the American Sign languages only. Here the model is trained with segmented greyscale gesture image, and the background subtraction from the image is not possible.

[2]. Anna Deza and Danial Hasan, in their research paper proposed a sign language recognition system which works based on Convolution Neural network. The data set used is American Sign Language Dataset which includes only single-handed gesture recognition. By using this model, they have achieved 77.25% accuracy in real-time. They have used image enhancement to make the model more accurate.

[3]. Aman Pathak, Avinash Kumar, Priyam, Priyanshu Gupta and Gunjan Chugh, in their research, introduced a real-time sign language detection model based on Convolutional Neural Network and they have used a pretrained SSD Mobile net V2 architecture. To create the model, they have used custom dataset. As it was a custom dataset, they have only used American Sign Languages. The model can recognise the sign languages in real time with an accuracy of 88 to 90%.

[4]. Amrita Thakur, Punjan Budhathoki, sarmila Upreti, Shirish Shrestha, and Subarna Shakya, in their research introduced American Sign Language Recognition using Convolution Neural Network and OpenCV. They have used American Sign Language dataset. The dataset is pre-processed using python libraries and trained using CNN VGG-16 model. Here they have converted the recognized input into speech. It also focuses on text to sign language conversion.

[5]. Veronica J. Schmalz in her research proposed a Realtime Italian Sign Language Recognition with Deep Learning. They have used Italian Sign Language for developing the model. The system can recognize Italian Sign Languages with an accuracy of 90%. The model used here is trained from scratch using CNN and VGG19. They have evaluated the model using OpenCV. But the process of extracting the actual image from the background takes a little more time. This affects the model performance a little bit.

IV. PROPOSED SYSTEM

The proposed Indian Sign Language Recognition System is able to detect the Indian sign languages more accurately. The system mainly works on three stages. The first stage includes the collection of hand gestures using OpenCV and label the images using labelImage package. The second phase consists of training the model. For training the model we have used machine learning with the help of packages such as TensorFlow. The third stage is all about recognizing the different sign languages in real-time. For real-time recognition mediaPipe library is used.

The research paper works on an Indian sign language recognition system which is implemented in python language. The dataset related to Indian sign languages are rarely available as compared to other sign languages. So, for efficiently recognizing the sign language we have used custom Indian sign language dataset. The major advantage is that we can extend the dataset by introducing more and more hand gestures which are used for communication.

Fig.1 Proposed architecture to detect sign language

A. Collecting gestures

This can be referred to the process of collecting images for deep learning using webcam and OpenCV. Here we import necessary packages and setting up a directory for storing the collected images. The labels for those images are created and specified the number of images collect for each label. Then the images are collected using webcam. A specific number of images for each gesture are captured and stored in the separate folders for each label.

B. Labelling images

The second step involved is labelling image for the gesture detection. For that it is needed to install the labelImage package. The collected images are labelled by running the labeling.py file in the labelImage package. The images in the directory are labelled according to the labels that are previously given. Here all the collected gestures are labelled and stored in the directory. The annotation for each gesture is created while labelling the images. Here the gestures are split into train and test in a ratio 7:3. For each image the label map are created according to the annotation.

C. Creating TensorFlowRecords

After creating the label maps the actual training process are started. Before that, the tensor flow record or TF records must be created. The TF records for the train and test are created. Once the TF records are created, the TensorFlow pretrained models from TensorFlow Zoo are used. Th steps involved here are

- Downloading pretrained Models.
- Creating pre-trained pipeline config.
- Creating custom model.

D. Training the model

For training the convolutional neural network we use the custom created dataset. The model is trained with the parameters from the model config file which list the learning rate, batch size and number of epochs. The feature extracted dataset which contains the gestures are used to train the model.

Fig 2. Model training process

E. Detecting in realtime

Once the training is completed the model can detect the sign languages in real-time. For real time detection we use webcam. The images or gestures are captured using the webcam and the corresponding label or text according to the detected gesture is displayed.

V. RESULT

In the real-time testing the proposed system can recognise the sign languages with high accuracy. By using the enhanced computer vision in the model, the problems occur due to lower image quality and background of the image can be avoided to a great extent. The model can recognise all the gestures in the custom dataset with an accuracy of 96 %. Furthermore, custom gestures can be easily integrated, and more gestures can be taken from different angles to improve the efficiency of the model.

Fig 3. System detecting different gestures

VI.CONCLUSION

The need of a better sign language recognition system arises in the recent times. This paper introduces a Convolutional Neural Network based model which uses the libraries such as OpenCV and mediaPipe can recognize the Indian sign languages. Unlike other models the model can recognize almost all the sign languages with high accuracy. The paper presents a vision-based system which can interpret Indian sign languages. The proposed system is tested in real time and the result are analyzed and compared with existing system. The improved version of python packages such as OpenCV and mediaPipe helps in easy deployment of the model. The real-time test of this model proved that the model could recognize almost all the gestures which are used for training. The existing system for sign language detection is struggled with the process of extracting the gestures from background and the proposed system can solve that problem to a great extent.

VII.FUTURE WORK

The system can be introduced to various sign languages and can be trained efficiently by using neural network. By using datasets which consist of different sign languages, a centralized sign language recognition can be created, which can recognize all sign languages. We can create much more efficient system introducing text to speech modules which converts sign languages to audio. Also, can integrate optimized model to AI systems like Amazon Alexa. Model can be trained further with optimized dataset and can make it able to recognize and subtract the hand gesture from background which yield better result.

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